

Online Consumer Behavior

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Introduction

A customer is a person who pays a little bit for the goods needed to be consumed in the form of goods and services. Similarly, consumers play an important role in the economy of the nation. Without consumer demand, producers will not have one of the main motivations to produce.

Consumer behavior is the study of how individual consumers, groups or organizations select, purchase, use and dispose of ideas, goods and services to meet their needs and wants. It refers to the actions of consumers in the market and the underlying motives of those actions.

The business sector and the revolutionary changes in the information technology sector, coupled with the choice of consumers, with the shopping situation and payment. The mechanisms are also broadened. Buyers now have the alternative option. Shop online for a product or availing of a product as well as offline. With the increasing penetration of the internet, these methods of buying have become increasingly popular today. People have so many choices to make with reference venues, but the most recent one is buying through internet online shoppingmode.

Objectives of the Study

- To Know the consumers attitude towards online Shopping
- To understand the consumers preferences in online shopping
- To understand the problems facing by consumers in online shopping
- To have a clear picture regarding how business opportunity is been utilized by the producers in helping consumers.

Meaning of Online Consumer Behavior

It is a type of behavior to the behavior of consumers buy online to meet their needs, search, select and purchase goods and services, and e-tailer while browsing websites in order to fulfill their needs.

Consumer behavior by individuals, groups, or organizations, and the purchase, use, and precede or follow the activities of the

customer’s emotional, mental and behavioral responses adhyavanavagidegrahakana the conduct of all activities related to the disposal of goods and services, including marketing the region as a distinct sub-discipline emerged in the 1940s and 50s. The study of consumer behavior relates to all aspects of purchase behavior - from pre-purchase activities to post-purchase use, valuation and disposal activities. It concerns all individuals who participate directly or indirectly in purchasing decisions and consumption activities, including brand-influencers and opinion leaders. Research has shown that it is difficult for experts in the field to monitor customer behavior. However, new research methods such as ethnography and consumer neuroscience are shedding new light on how consumers make decisions.

History of Online Shopping

1979	Michael Aldrich invented online shopping
1982	Minitel was introduced in France and was used for online ordering
1990	The first World Wide Web server and browser created by Tim-Berners- Lee .
1994	online banking, the opening of an online pizza shop. Amazon.com launched its online shopping site
1995	eBay was introduced.
1998	PayPal comes into existence
2002	eBay acquires PayPal for \$1.5 billion and changes the scope of online shopping forever
2003	Alibaba's sites Taobao (In China)
2007	Flipkart was founded by Sachin Bansal and Binny Bansal
2010	Snapdeal
2011	Shopclues
2013	Amazon in India

Distinction between Traditional and e-business

This difference gives us clarity about the customer behavior in online transaction. Few differences are :

Basis of Distinction	Traditional Business	e-business
Ease of Formation	Difficult	Simple
Physical presence	Required	Not Required
Locational requirements	Proximity towards the source of raw materials or the market for the products	None
Operating cost	High	Low
Nature of contact	Indirect	Direct
Opportunity of Inter personal touch	Much More	Less
Ease of going global	Less	More

Nature of Human capital	Semi skilled and even unskilled manpower	Technically and professionally qualified personnel
Transaction risk	Low	High
Nature of Internal communication	Hierarchical	Non Hierarchical

Buying Online - Consumer Reasons

- Convenience : Online shopping happens 24/7.
- Saving Time : Reduces travelling time, waiting time.
- Easy in Comparing : Between different products, design, colour, price etc.
- Discounts : Discount offers on special days.
- Privacy : No other person get to know about the shopping.

Factors Influencing Consumer Behavior

Cultural Factors	Social Factors	Personal Factors	Psychological Factors
Culture	Family	Age	Beliefs
Social Class	Role	Interest	Motivation
Tradition	Status	Occupation	Attitude
Values	Friends	Life style	Experience

Cultural Factors

Consumer behavior is deeply influenced by the cultural factors involved in it. There are three sub-factors namely buyer culture, subculture and social subcategories. Culture, It gives birth to traditions, values, riches and customer attitudes and several other factors.

Culture is part and parcel of every society. A person’s desires and behavior. When we move from one country to another, the Culture changes and this also matters a lot.

Social Factors

Social features of consumer customers are also identified as critical, This has a major impact on customer behavior. The most important social Factors include reference groups, family, character and status. Reference Groups a group of people who influence a person because they are a member Wants to be a member of it or not. One person may belong to many Reference groups at a time. Various reference groups, family members, Friends, neighboring colleagues, religious groups, professional groups, aspiration group.

Personal Factors

Many studies on demographic factors refer to the social factor as well consumer behavior. Personal factors include age, gender, education, occupation, income, lifecycle stage, lifestyle, personality and self-concept. Consumer’s aspects like thinking, searching, and processing information, decision-making and evaluation of products or services varies because of the influence of the personal factors. Age and life-cycle have significant influence on consumer buying behavior. The taste, preference, and behavioral changes in the age and A buyer of the life cycle phase. Income of a buyer also acts as a predictor of its purchase Behavior.

Pyschological Factors

Factors which includes Influence for the behavior of the consumers. ‘, motivation’, ‘, perception’, LEARNING ‘, and’, is derived, as explained The sum of attitude Motivation of the can be is also the Desire that is generated Because of Events. Events for The intensity of the at WHEN is very Do multiplex, IT gets converted into HIGH Motive. Everyone has a flexible approach to have an impact on the lives of everyone and that affects, and other people will react to objects or events .The seller will get the best help for its willingness to realize that by analyzing customers’ feedback.

Consumer Buying Process

Need for the Product

When there is a marked difference between the customers and desired the difference between the actual situation and is caused by the customer’s actual or desired situation changes. Then he /

she will remove the gap between the actual and the desired situation in the work of significance can be interpreted as provides the necessary high level of identified need If it's really important to be fulfilled, then the customer will move on for the purchase of the product.

Search for the Information

The customer is now possible to gather information about the product they are marked with the requirements of includes information that may be important as product features, brand, and price-related information to the seller major sources in general print media, radio, television, in Internet Advertising.

Purchase

The process steps for the purchase of consumer real aim of the unique features of the product and the brand after reaching the options available to moving to leverage the product to the customer features and function, in addition to the purchase decision of the customer's decision at this point is also affected by the contents of his shopping experience, the quality orStore promotion, the availability of a return policy or better terms and conditions of sale.

Post Purchase Evaluation

The consumer decision-making process ends with a post-purchase evaluation. When a customer starts using the product side by side, he continues to evaluate it. The Depending on the customer or the customer may feel satisfied or dissatisfied The level of performance of the purchased product. This assessment is affected Consumer future purchase decision.

Conclusion

Online shopping has been a concern since the era of the New World to everyone online wants to be part of the world. Online shopping on the web is focused mainly on Building Trust in the physical location of a seller to change the world, due to the new virtual site. Which leads to the belief that online purchase of an influence on the goal of change . The most obvious aspects of online consumer behavior in time, money, efforts have remained constant .It has come to play a simple integrated model of consumer behavior has been observed that there is a strong need for complex models. Today's consumers are intelligent technology and technology have advanced stages of self-Learning.

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